

1 **NOD2 controls expression of the cancer susceptibility CASC gene family.**

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7 We observed alteration in expression of genes encoded by the cancer susceptibility (CASC) family in the
8 primary cells of humans with Crohn's Disease containing mutation of the NOD2 sensor. In a heterologous
9 system wherein human cells were engineered to stably express wild-type human NOD2, NOD2 could
10 control the expression of CASC4. CASC4 regulation by a NOD2 frameshift mutant containing a
11 carboxy-terminal truncation in the LRR domain was significantly impaired.

12 Citations

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